

ORGANIZING CLASSES IN TRAINING WORKSHOPS THROUGH ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL EXPERIENCES

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Abstract. *To study and popularize advanced pedagogical practices of the teacher, to develop his political consciousness, to expand his professional knowledge and experience, to form his knowledge and skills in the field of education.*

Keywords: *education and upbringing, professional qualification, pedagogical skills, methodology, didactic materials, educational tools.*

A specialist teacher plays a leading role in providing education and training to students. The state of the educational process, the level of preparation of students depends on the teacher's professional qualifications, pedagogical skills, and the level of culture.

Individual methodical work is carried out according to the plan drawn up for the whole academic year. It envisages individual methodical researches for teacher engineer-pedagogue in order to deepen their pedagogical skills and knowledge.

They include: preparation of lectures on pedagogical topics; creating methodical instructions on the most difficult topics of the curriculum; defines problematic research work that requires a lot of work. These assignments are a mandatory minimum for every pedagogue.

The work plan of each pedagogue, engineer-pedagogue should consist of four sections:

1. Raising the ideological and political level.
2. Improving methodological and pedagogical skills.
3. Expansion and deepening of scientific and technical knowledge in the field of the type of work being taught.
4. Improvement of knowledge and skills in the field of organization of pedagogue's work on a scientific basis.

This plan will be reviewed and approved at the methodical board meeting. Reports of teachers and engineer-pedagogues will be heard about the implementation of this plan.

Raising the ideological-political level - when developing materials, it is necessary to take into account contemporary life and production.

The essence of teaching young people in the field of labor education and agriculture is to study the works, presidential decisions related to the profession, participate in political seminars and theoretical conferences, get acquainted with the current policy through the press, radio, television and apply it in practical work.

Improvement of methodological and pedagogical skills - improvement of the form of educational work with students in the prepared lectures, instructions, recommendations.

The independent work of the teacher of vocational education is to regularly familiarize himself with scientific magazines and works related to the specialty, and to improve the quality of training in his methodological skills, to prepare new methodological instructions, to solve the problem of activating students' cognitive activities, and to help spread advanced pedagogical experiences among other teachers.

The teacher who entered the theory classes to check that he has a schedule of classes and a plan for each lesson, as well as a lecture text for the lesson; compliance with the plan and program on the subject of the lesson; that educational tools are effectively used; assessment of the implementation of educational work in the lesson and its implementation, appropriateness of the type of lesson chosen to solve the set goal; it is necessary to pay attention to the correct selection of the structure of the lesson, the time spent, and the preparation of the teacher and students for the lesson.

Expanding and deepening scientific and technological knowledge in the field of teaching type - regular technology and rational work, technical news will be achieved. Practical skills and qualities are improved by mastering advanced methods of training under qualified methods of professionalism and manufacturing facilities of teachers of professional education.

Improving the knowledge and skills of teaching in the field of scientific basis. Regular supply of the necessary materials, regular support with equipment, the organization of workplaces on scientific grounds is achieved through the scientific basis of the most effective use of technical means.

Preparation of didactic materials

Our tools used as a resource for theoretical and practical training differ as follows:

Often, educational materials are used simultaneously as didactic materials, that is, for teaching and learning.

Preparation of educational and didactic materials means their selection by the teacher and adaptation to the purpose of theoretical or practical training.

If there are no ready-made tools, then the teacher has to prepare them himself.

When preparing educational and didactic materials, the practical teacher should pay attention to the following, taking into account the limited time and technical capabilities:

- sketches for worksheets, handouts (copies of printed texts), slides, blackboard images;
- question papers for written assignments, written and oral tests;
- assessment sheet, control sheet;
- work plans, organizational documents.

Materials for the teacher include not only information related to the field, but also information on organizational activities, methods and evaluation of results. Student materials, as a rule, contain only aspects relevant to the field.

While didactic materials are aimed at students, teaching may differ from materials. For example: worksheets, quizzes, guiding method questions and specific handouts.

Materials distributed to students should contain the following information:

- educational texts written in simple language
- blank spaces in texts (to be filled in by students)
- questions that allow the student to think freely
- clear drawings (sketches) and tables, intended for work in the workshop, showing the stages of work

- information about material, equipment, tools and auxiliary means.

One of the newest methods of text preparation is color separation of texts:

- white papers: texts on content aspects (for teachers and students)
- green papers: tasks for students
- red papers: teacher's methodical documents and assignment answer sheets

Color coding makes documents easier to use

The same method is used to prepare seminar documents.

To prepare the slides:

- ordinary acetate paper or transparent artificial paper;
- slides with special layers that can be copied;
- alcohol for cleaning felt-tip, permanent and water-soluble slides;
- drawing devices (template, ruler, etc.) are used.

To prepare slides manually:

- picture or text is sketched on paper
- the slide is placed on it and fixed with a velcro
- the sample photo is copied to the slide.

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